

Multi-class Sentiment Analysis on Twitter

Venkatesh*, Nagaraju Y*, Sheema Sultana*+, Mamthaj A*, Priyadarshini R*, Kavya S*

*Department of Computer Science and Engineering

*University Visvesvaraya College of Engineering, Bangalore University, Bangalore 560 001

*venkateshm.uvce@bub.ernet.in

*+sheemasultana11@gmail.com

Abstract—Twitter, Online Social Networks (OSN) moved toward becoming truly the stage for individuals express their contemplations, share their thoughts, opinion on real-time events and up coming occasions. Sentiment analysis is procedure of gathering, conglomeration, and classification of data gathered in social networks into a different emotion classes. Sentiment analysis and opinion mining in social networks are current research topics. The state of the art works focused on the binary and ternary classifications. These binary and ternary classifications hindrance the actual sentiments present in the tweets of user. However, existence of multiple meanings that might have different sentiment polarity for the same word, the binary classification fails to identify meaning and the polarity of slang words. To analyse opinion of user, it is necessary to go deeper in the classification and detect the sentiment hidden behind user post. Multi-class sentiment classification has always been a challenging task due to complexity of natural languages and the difficulty of understanding and mathematically quantifying how humans express their feelings. In this paper, we proposed model that performs the task of multi-class classification of online posts of Twitter users. It demonstrates how far it is possible to go with the classification, and the limitations of handling the slang words, hashtags used in the tweets. Our implementation demonstrates that proposed approach achieves an accuracy about 45.19% on the multi-class classification for the dataset (text emotion). For dataset (Consumer complaint) the proposed approach achieves accuracy of 82.07%. The approach achieve better accuracy due to the number of features extracted from the individual datasets.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online Social Networks (OSN) is platform for the people to express opinions, attitudes and emotions toward an events, movie, products or individual. Twitter is one such Online Social Networks that allows people to share their opinion about real-time events such as politics, sports and social events. Ease of access and open to post real-time updates, replying to post quickly attract the people more than ever. The collection of tweets presents abundant source of data mine. Tweeter provides clickable link "hashtag" when user tweet. It is easy to search tweets using the hashtags in Tweeter. With help of the hashtags twitter enable user to follow other user even in the absence of mutual relation. The peoples opinions, attitudes and emotions toward an entity can be annotated according to their polarity. It is easy to collect all related tweets on specific topic from several users and analyze people's opinion towards specific service or product. The service provider or manufacturing company collects all related user tweets that behave their services or products. The traced tweets are analyzed to asses the level of user satisfaction or user expectation on product or upcoming services. This

classification process is called sentiment analysis. The user's opinion and sentiment expressed in a text are analyzed in the classification process. A binary classification classify all review or opinion into positive or negative sentiments for a particular product or service.

A. Literature Survey

In recent years, multi-class sentiment analysis on Twitter has drawn the lot of attention of researcher community. The sentiment analysis and opinion extraction on Twitter present a hot topic of research. Twitter present a huge source of data representing the user's thoughts, expressions, opinions towards various topics and subjects. Performing sentiment analysis on such data is paramount important for companies, individual and data scientist.

The state-of-art-works dealt with the actual content of tweets and focused on classifying tweets into sentiment polarity (positive or negative). Multi-class classification refers to the identification of the exact sentiment(s) present in a given tweets rather than finding the its overall polarity (whether it is positive, negative or neutral). Seven approaches: the naive method, support vector regression method, the linear regression, the auto-regressive, the exponential smoothing technique were used to analyze twitter text and sentiment in twitter. Several authors have proposed the specific methods for sentiment analysis and tweet text classification on data collected from Twitter as well as other source of online social network. In the last few years, decent number of recent papers have been published that address the classification of tweets and sentiment analysis. However, the nature of the classification and the features used for classification vary depending on the aim.

Authors in [1] demonstrated the significance of Twitter as a great source of data, they presents method to extract and determine the polarity from the data that users post. The authors also worked multiclassification of twitter texts, classification of texts collected from Twitter and classifies these texts into multiple sentiment classes.

In recent years, multi-class sentiment analysis on Twitter has drawn the lot of attention of researcher community. The sentiment analysis and opinion extraction on Twitter present a hot topic of research. Twitter present a huge source of data representing the user thoughts, expression opinions towards various topics and subjects. Performing sentiment analysis on such data is paramount important for companies, individual and data scientist.

The state-of-art-works dealt with the actual content of tweets and focused on classifying tweets into sentiment polarity (positive or negative). Multi-class classification refers to the identification of the exact sentiment(s) present in a given tweets rather than finding the its overall polarity (whether it is positive, negative or neutral). Seven approaches: the naive method, support vector regression method, the linear regression, the auto-regressive, the exponential smoothing technique were used to analyze twitter text and sentiment in twitter

The Twitter Sentiment Analysis is not only used in extracting opinions from the tweets but also widely in the field of health care. Monitoring drug abuse, detecting the adverse effect of drugs by scanning the tweets with the drug names and finding its corresponding symptoms. The proposed method [2] is to identify the adverse drug effects from tweets by modelling it as a link classification problem in graphs. Drug and symptom mentions are extracted from the tweet history of each user and a drug symptom graph is built, where nodes represent either drugs or symptoms and edges are labelled positive or negative, for desired or adverse drug effects respectively. have been used for monitoring drug abuse, adverse reactions to drug usage, and analyzing expression of sentiments related to drugs.

In the last few years, a hot topic of research field is on Twitter sentiment analysis. The decent number of recent papers have been published that address the classification of tweets and sentiment analysis. However, the nature of the classification and the features used for classification vary depending on the aim.

In recent years, multi-class sentiment analysis on Twitter has drawn the lot of attention of researcher community. The sentiment analysis and opinion extraction on Twitter present a hot topic of research. Twitter present a huge source of data representing the user thoughts, expression opinions towards various topics and subjects. Performing sentiment analysis on such data is paramount important for companies, individual and data scientist.

The state-of-art-works dealt with the actual content of tweets and focused on classifying tweets into sentiment polarity (positive or negative). Multi-class classification refers to the identification of the exact sentiment(s) present in a given tweets rather than finding the its overall polarity (whether it is positive, negative or neutral). Seven approaches: the naive method, support vector regression method, the linear regression, the auto-regressive, the exponential smoothing technique were used to analyze twitter text and sentiment in twitter unstructured tweets on Twitter provides the platform to obtain valuable information by analyzing online users comments, and emotions polarity towards the service or product. Authors in [10] used sentiment analysis, text mining to predict the satisfaction of car buyer and number of sales in particular month. Yahya et al.[11] have used Naive Bayes and Random Forest algorithm to classify the tweets and predict sentiment polarity. Amalgamated sentiment polarity aid determine stock price. Alalwan et al. [8] developed a model to represent peoples opinion on prevailing critical issues. The success of movie at box-office with help of word-of-mouth is predicted using the support vector machines and the Naive Bayesian classifier[9]. Authors in [1] has used deep learning algorithms

to analyze sentiment of the tweets and convolutions neural networks, recurrent neural networks (RNN) to construct prediction model.

Rapid growth of Twitter provides an opportunity for people from different cultural and psychological backgrounds to express thoughts, opinions. Though twitter forbid posting hate speech, but it difficult to control twitter content. It is necessity to find twitter content that contains hateful sentence or words that inciting to hatred. Authors in [4] designed a model based on uni-grams and patterns to determine the Hate speech contents that has offensive language and spoil the symphony in the society or getting a specific group of people. It is difficult to determine sarcastic texts in twitter. Therefore, Authors in [5] designed a pattern-based technique to determine sarcasm, criticism or mockery.

Tibetan micro-blogs contains Chinese, and English words. It is difficult to determine emoticons, the grammar , and the opinions. Authors in [6]developed a sentiment classification method for Tibetan micro-blogs based on multifeature fusion.

Tweets on sports reflect feelings and their opinions on player or event. Given football events, it is difficult to analyse the tweets posted by football fans through, because tweets that reflect changes in the fans sentiment as they watch the game and react to the events of the game. Authors in [7]designed a domain-specific model for understanding sentiments expressed in football fans conversations.

Authors in [12] proposed the method that determines the new price of *Bitcoin* based on RNN model, historical price of Bitcoin and tweets collected from different accounts. Deep learning algorithms and convolution neural network have been used for image and voice processing. In recent years, convolution neural network is used for movie reviews classification and sentiment analysis [13]. The unsupervised learning algorithms are used to find the dependent semantic and statistical characteristics of tweet text. These semantically embedded words with n-grams and sentiment polarity score of words forms feature set. The feature set fed as input the deep convolution neural network to predict the classify sentiments labels for given set of tweets. These word embedding are combined with n-grams features and word sentiment polarity score features to form a sentiment feature set of tweets [14]

Inter-domain sentiment classifier is required as Twitter being used by peoples of different background and culture. It is difficult to have universal sentiment classifier to classify diversified tweets on Twitter because tweets are unlabelled, unrated and topics are diverse in Twitter. Shenghua et. al [15] designed semi-supervised classifier that classify the unlabelled data and topic-related tweets. Twitter is platform to express thoughts, opinions and large-scale repositories of tweets. It provide an opportunities for data scientist to know pulse of the nation [16]. With user-generate tweets on Twitter it is easy to explore the depression and emotional patterns relating to mental health[17] The use of Twitter as tool to evaluate user satisfaction properly and timely[18] User satisfaction is an important aspect to consider in any public transport system, and as such, regular and sound measurements of its levels are fundamental. However, typical evaluation schemes involve costly and time-consuming surveys.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Twitter based sentiment analysis has attracted the research community. Twitter provides platforms on which users post their thoughts, opinions and find public opinion about the events or satisfaction level of products/service. Given the influence of Twitter, the analysis of Twitter contents, find out all the sentiments hidden in a given tweet and classify the Twitter contents into different categories is required.

III. PROPOSED WORK

Multiclass classification is the problem of classifying instances into one of three or more classes. Given a set of tweets, we aim to classify each one of them to one of the following 5 classes: 'happiness', 'worry', 'neutral', 'hate' and 'sadness'. Therefore, from each tweet, we extract different sets of features, refer to a training set and use machine learning algorithms to perform the classification. We have chosen the aforementioned sentiment classes because these are the most commonly expressed sentiments.

In this paper the data-set collected is passed as input to the training process along with the labels. The tweets in the data-set are programmatically divided into training and test data set. We perform the pre-processing on the data to clean all the unwanted contents and extract only the valuable inputs that fed into classifier as input. This process is referred to as *Feature Extraction*. The extracted features are converted to their numeric values which are called vectors. These vectors are then passed to the machine learning classifier as input. Using these inputs the classifier tries to associate each class with its corresponding label using test samples and a model is generated. Using this model we can now predict the sentiment of the unseen data, where the classifier predicts sentiment for the unseen tweet through its learning experience in the training process.

A. Pre-Processing Dataset

In preprocessing of tweet includes, replace apostrophes with its fullest form, splitting of the hashtags (e.g. #muchfun to much fun), replacing slang words with their original forms (e.g. tysm to thank you so much) and correct the spellings (e.g. kool to cool). From the tweets remove all URLs (e.g. www.xyz.com), delete mentions (username), smileys, Email-ids, and reserved words. The sequence of repeated characters, punctuations, symbols, numbers are removed from tweets, Finally, lemmatization (that is convert a word to its base form (e.g. running to run) is performed.

B. Tokenization

Tokenization is a step which splits longer strings of text into smaller pieces, or tokens. Larger chunks of text can be tokenized into sentences, sentences can be tokenized into words, etc. Further processing is generally performed after a piece of text has been appropriately tokenized. Tokenization is also referred to as text segmentation or lexical analysis. In this paper, each token represents an individual word and together forms a feature set for each particular tweet. During tokenization stop words are removed to extract the main features from the given pre-processed data.

C. Feature Selection

Feature selection is also called variable selection or attribute selection. It is the automatic selection of attributes in your data (such as columns in tabular data) that are most relevant to the predictive modeling problem you are working on. It can be used to identify and remove unneeded, irrelevant and redundant attributes from data that do not contribute to the accuracy of a predictive model or may in fact decrease the accuracy of the model. These features are then passed through the classifier in order to train the model. Feature selection is process of selecting a subset of relevant features for use in model construction. Feature selection acts as filter, muting out feature that are not useful in addition to our existing feature. Feature selection method aid us to create an accurate predictive model helps us for choosing features that will give us a good or better accuracy whilst requiring data.

IV. CLASSIFIER ALGORITHMS

Naive Bayes is the most straightforward and fast classification algorithm. It has two phases, a learning phase, and the evaluation phase. In the learning phase, classifier trains its model on a given dataset and in the evaluation phase, it tests the classifier performance. Performance is evaluated on the basis of various parameters such as accuracy, error, precision, and recall.

Naive Bayes Algorithm:

Input : Training Dataset T, F = (f₁, f₂, f₃,..., f_n)

Output : A class of testing dataset.

Steps: 1. Read the training dataset T;

2. Calculate the mean and standard deviation of the predictor variables in each class;

3. Calculate the probability of f_i, using the gauss density equation in each class; Until the probability of all predictor variables f₁, f₂, f₃,..., f_n has been calculated.

4. Calculate the likelihood of each class;

5. Get the greatest likelihood;

Logistic Regression Classifier: Logistic regression is known and used as a linear classifier. It is used to come up with a hyperplane in feature space to separate observations that belong to a class from all the other observations that do not belong to that class. The decision boundary is thus linear. Robust and efficient implementations are readily available to use logistic regression as a linear classifier.

Random Forest Classifier: Random forests are an ensemble learning method for classification and regression. Random Forest is a supervised learning algorithm. It creates a forest and makes it somehow random. The forest it builds, is an ensemble of Decision Trees, most of the time trained with the bagging method. Random forest builds multiple decision trees and merges them together and the output is predicted by taking majority voting of all the individual decision trees outcome to get a more accurate and stable prediction.

Linear Support Vector Classifier:The objective of a Linear SVC is to fit to the data you provide, returning a "best fit" hyperplane that divides, or categorizes, your data. From there, after getting the hyperplane, we can then feed some features to

Algorithm 1 Random Forest Algorithm

```

procedure SELCANDIDATESPLITDIM(TreeRoot,
min(1+Poisson( $\lambda$ ),D))
  for t = 0 do
    Receive( $X_t, Y_t, I_t$ )
    From the environment
     $A_t \leftarrow \text{leafcontaining}X_t$ 
    if  $I_t = \text{estimation}$  then
      UpdateEstimationStatistics( $A_t, (X_t, Y_t)$ )
    for all S  $\in$  candidateSplits( $A_t$ ) do
      for all A  $\in$  CandidatesChildren(S) do
        if  $X_t \in A$  then
          UpdateEstiStat(A, ( $X_t, Y_t$ ))
        end if
      end for
    end for
    if  $I_t = \text{Structure}$  then
      if  $A_t$  has fewer than m candidate split points then
        for all d  $\in$  CandidateSplitDimensions( $A_t$ ) do
          CreateCandidateSplit( $A_t, d, \pi d X_t$ )
        end for
      end if
    for S  $\in$  CandidateSplits( $A_t$ ) do
      for all A  $\in$  CandidateChildren(S) do
        if  $X_t \in A$  then
          UpdateEstiStat(A, ( $X_t, Y_t$ ))
        end if
      end for
    end for
    if CanSplit( $A_t$ ) then
      if ShouldSplit( $A_t$ ) then
        Split( $A_t$ )
      else if
        MustSplit( $A_t$ ) then
          Split( $A_t$ )
        end if
      end if
    end for
  end procedure

```

your classifier to see what the "predicted" class is. The support Vector Machines is considered to be a classification approach, it but can be employed in both types of classification and regression problems. It can easily handle multiple continuous and categorical variables. SVM constructs a hyperplane in multidimensional space to separate different classes. SVM generates optimal hyperplane in an iterative manner, which is used to minimize an error. The core idea of SVM is to find a maximum marginal hyperplane (MMH) that best divides the dataset into classes.

V. RESULTS

A. Dataset

Imbalanced data typically refers to a problem with classification where the classes are not represented equally. The dataset does not have equal number of instances in each class.

TABLE I
DATA SET

Sentiment classes	Number of tweets
Happiness	9072
Hate	1453
Neutral	8657
Sadness	5185
Worry	8478

Imbalanced classes affects the performance of the classifier which varies across the different Machine Learning Classifiers. Below we provide the distribution of our dataset in terms of number of tweets in each class:

B. Performance parameters

Accuracy It is the number of correct predictions made divided by the total number of predictions made. Accuracy does not perform well with imbalanced data sets.

Precision is the fraction of relevant instances among the retrieved instances. The precision for a class is the number of true positives (i.e. the number of items correctly labeled as belonging to the positive class) divided by the total number of elements labeled as belonging to the positive class (i.e. the sum of true positives and false positives, which are items incorrectly labelled as belonging to the class).

Recall is the fraction of relevant instances that have been retrieved over the total amount of relevant instances Recall in this context is defined as the number of true positives divided by the total number of elements that actually belong to the positive class.

F-score: A measure that combines precision and recall is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, the traditional F-measure or balanced F-score

Support The support is the number of occurrences of each particular class in the true responses (responses in your test set).

C. Performance Analysis

The above figure gives the comparison of the 4 classifiers which we used to train the data with respect to the accuracy. Going from ascending order, Random Forest is least accurate with about 40% accuracy, Linear SVC and Multinomial nave bayes give about 44% and Logistic Regression gives high performance with 46% accuracy.

The above figure 1 gives the comparison of the 4 classifiers which we used to train the data with respect to the accuracy. Going from ascending order, Random Forest is least accurate with about 40% accuracy, Linear SVC and Multinomial nave bayes give about 44% and Logistic Regression gives high performance with 46% accuracy. Figure 2 is the plotted graph of number of features vs accuracy of 3 different classification models as follows: The multi-class sentiment analysis dataset which we used in our work with 5 classes gives

- The multi-class sentiment analysis dataset which we used in our work with 5 classes gives only about 5924 features

Fig. 1. Accuracy of the classifiers

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
happiness	0.57	0.66	0.61	2961
hate	0.51	0.12	0.19	466
neutral	0.42	0.51	0.46	2814
sadness	0.40	0.18	0.25	1764
worry	0.40	0.43	0.41	2777
accuracy			0.46	10782
macro avg	0.46	0.38	0.38	10782
weighted avg	0.46	0.46	0.44	10782

Fig. 2. Measure of performance with respect to Logistic Regression Classifier

with accuracy of 45.19% when trained using Logistic Regression.

- The multi-class customer complaint dataset with 12 classes gives about 8000 features and accuracy of 82.07% when trained using Linear SVC.
- The binary dataset having 2 classes positive and negative gives out 12663 features and accuracy of 74% when trained using Nave Bayes classifier.

Figure 3 is the confusion matrix table. It is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a Logistic Regression Classifier on a set of test data for which the true values are known. Figure 4 is the confusion matrix table. It is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier on a set of test data for which the true values are known. Figure 5 is the confusion matrix table. It is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a MRandom Forest Classifier on a set of test data for which the true values are known. Figure 6 is the confusion matrix table. It is a table that is often used to describe the performance of a MLinear SVC Classifier on a set of test data for which the true values are known.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix for Logistic Regression Classifier

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix for Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix for Random Forest Classifier

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix for Linear SVC Classifier

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Multi-class classification can detect the sentiment hidden behind users post, and it helps to analyse the opinion of the user. The complexity of natural languages and the difficulty of understanding and mathematically quantifying how humans express their feelings is challenging task in multi-class classification. Initially, the collected dataset is pre-processed by cleaning the unwanted contents in the tweet which does not give any relevant information about the expressed opinion. The features are extracted from the pre-processed data and these features are passed as an input to the classifier. The classifier then learns to associate each input with the corresponding output (sentiment) from the data samples provided in the training process. Once the model is trained, for a given unseen tweet, the model can predict the sentiment for the tweet.

The proposed model for multi-class classification achieves an accuracy of 45.19% for 5 different sentiment classes compared to an accuracy of 74% for binary classification. In this paper, Random Forest, Multinomial Nave Bayes, Linear SVC and Logistic Regression classifiers were used to train our model. From our experiments, Logistic Regression proved to be more accurate for the dataset used in the project. The proposed model can represent the different sentiments and show how these sentiments are related.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jianqiang, Zhao and Xiaolin, Gui, "Comparison research on text pre-processing methods on twitter sentiment analysis" *IEEE Access*, vol.5, pp. 2870–2879, 2017.
- [2] Mahata, Debanjan and Friedrichs, Jasper and Shah, Rajiv Ratn and Jiang, Jing "Detecting personal intake of medicine from twitter" *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol.33, no.4, pp.87-95, 2018.
- [3] Feizollah, Ali and Ainin, Sulaiman and Anuar, "Halal Products on Twitter: Data Extraction and Sentiment Analysis Using Stack of Deep Learning Algorithms" *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 83354–83362, 2019
- [4] Watanabe, Hajime and Bouazizi, Mondher and Ohtsuki, Tomoaki, "Hate speech on twitter: A pragmatic approach to collect hateful and offensive expressions and perform hate speech detection, *IEEE Access*, Vol.6, pp.1382513835, 2018

- [5] Bouazizi, Mondher and Ohtsuki, Tomoaki Otsuki "A pattern-based approach for sarcasm detection on twitter" *IEEE Access*, vol.4, pp. 5477–5488, 2016
- [6] Lirong and Lei, Qiao and Zhang, Zhen "Advanced sentiment classification of tibetan microblogs on smart campuses based on multi-feature fusion" *IEEE Access*, vol.6, pp.17896–17904, 2018
- [7] Aloufi, Samah and El Saddik, Abdulmotaleb, "Sentiment identification in football-specific tweets" *IEEE Access*, vol.6, pp.78609–78621, 2018
- [8] A. Alalwan, N. P. Rana, Y. K. Dwivedi, and R. Algharabat, "Social media in marketing: A review and analysis of the existing literature" *Journal on Telematics Information*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 11771190, 2017.
- [9] Y. Liu, and A. Whinston, "Whose and what chatter matters? The effect of tweets on movie sales" *Journal on Decision Support System*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 863870, 2013.
- [10] S. E. Shukri, R. I. Yaghi, I. Aljarah, and H. Alsawalqah "Twitter sentiment analysis: A case study in the automotive industry" In Proceedings of IEEE Jordan Conference on Applied Electrical Engineering Computing Technologies (AEECT) Amman, Jordan, Nov. 2015, pp. 15.
- [11] Cakra, Yahya Eru and Trisedya, Bayu Distawan "Stock price prediction using linear regression based on sentiment analysis" *IEEE International Conference on Advanced Computer Science and Information Systems (ICACSIS)*, pp. 147–154, 2015.
- [12] Pant, Bishnu Kumar "Recurrent Neural Network Based Bitcoin Price Prediction by Twitter Sentiment Analysis" *Proceedings of IEEE 3rd International Conference on Computing, Communication and Security (ICCCS)*, pp. 128132, 2018.
- [13] N. Kalchbrenner, E. Grefenstette, and P. Blunsom, "A Convolutional Neural Network for Modelling Sentences" *arXiv preprint arXiv:1408.5882* pp. 655666, Jun. 2014.
- [14] Jianqiang, Zhao, Gui Xiaolin, and Zhang Xuejun "Deep convolution neural networks for twitter sentiment analysis" *IEEE Access* vol 6, pp. 23253-23260, 2018
- [15] Liu, Shenghua and Cheng, Xueqi and Li, Fuxin and Li, Fangtao "TASC: topic-adaptive sentiment classification on dynamic tweets" *IEEE transactions on knowledge and data engineering*, Vol.27, No.6, pp.1696–1709, 2014.
- [16] Misllove, Alan "Pulse of the nation: US mood throughout the day inferred from twitter" <http://www.ccs.neu.edu/home/amislove/twittermood/>, pp. 23-34, 2010.
- [17] Larsen, Mark E and Boonstra, Tjeerd W and Batterham, Philip J and ODea, Bridianne and Paris, Cecile and Christensen, Helen "We feel: mapping emotion on Twitter" *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, Vol.19, No.4, pp.1246–1252, 2015.
- [18] Mendez, Jose Tomas and Lobel, Hans and Parra, Denis and Herrera, Juan Carlos "Using Twitter to Infer User Satisfaction With Public Transport: The Case of Santiago, Chile" *IEEE Access*, Vol.7, pp. 60255–60263, 2019